

Dimmons.net Research Group

STRATEGIC PLANNING 2018-2023

Executive Summary

Version 1.0 - April 2018

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1. Introduction

Created in January 2016, Dimmons.net is one of the ten research groups of the Internet Interdisciplinary Institute (IN3), a research center of the Open University of Catalonia (UOC). Dimmons group research focuses on socio economic innovation connected to digital technologies, and more concretely, on the collaborative economy and the Commons.

This is a report of the strategic planning process of Dimmons, which has been developed adopting a co-designed approach. Involving the diversity of its group's members and network of close collaborators, as well as other representative stakeholders, the goal has been to establish the strategic objectives for the research group from 2018 to 2023. This strategic planning of Dimmons follows the previous strategic planning of the IN3¹ and the UOC in 2016².

The development of the co-designed process, as well as this report, has been guided by Mayo Fuster (Dimmons's director) and it's part of a case study developed for the PhD project of Enric Senabre on co-creation methodologies applied to research innovation. In this sense the design of Dimmons, and this strategic planning, could be conceived as a meta-research process. As a process of design and implementation of a research group in order to tackle and reflect on: *"What are the organizational logics and strategies that favor the impact and resilience of research groups in a context of profound changes due to the transition to the Knowledge Society?"*. We developed this approach as an action-research looking for inspiration in the the precise area we are expert on: collaborative production. Thus, a secondary meta-research questions is: *"How far methodological innovations on collaborative production could provide guidelines and solutions to design resilient and successful research groups today?"*.

The organization of this report is twofold: First, a chapter presenting the state of the art on strategic planning for research and its connection with key issues in open science and transdisciplinarity, as well as an explanation of the methodology adopted. Secondly, a sequenced description of the strategic planning outputs, from the departing points of the group to the collaborative analysis, followed by the establishment of strategies around the agreed common goals.

¹ URL: <https://www.uoc.edu/portal/en/in3/coneix/pla-estrategic/index.htm>

² URL: <http://www.uoc.edu/portal/en/universitat/pla-estrategic/index.html>

2. State of the art, inspiration and methodological approach

2.1 State of the art on strategic planning for research

Despite the current competition between academic institutions for resources and prestige adopting evaluation systems, ranking mechanisms and performance indicators (Ordorika & Lloyd, 2015), there's little evidence on successful strategies and practices of research management (Derrick & Nickson, 2014). Specially when it comes to the additional need to adapt the production of scientific knowledge to collaborative and interdisciplinary approaches (Gibbons et al., 1994), in a context of networked academic organisations and researchers (Wang & Hicks, 2015) and the "participatory turn" of science (Jasanoff, 2003). In that sense, strategic planning seems one of the possible elements that can contribute to better management practices in scientific institutions (Wilbon, 2012), since collaborative practices in research need to balance flexibility with structured decision-making processes, as well as autonomy with shared long-term vision (Vom Brocke & Lippe, 2015).

This seems especially important in times of a needed merging in a Academia between Open Science approaches and wider Open Knowledge practices (Sidler, 2014), as well as the opportunity to explore dynamics of participative open innovation in research (Schildhauer & Voss, 2014). However, among the current challenges related to strategy and long term goals for scientific activity, we can find from individual and systemic obstacles for research openness (Scheliga & Friesike, 2014) to the recurrent crisis on the competition for impact factors and publication pressure (Binswanger, 2014). Beyond that, another relevant issue nowadays is the concept of scientific impact itself, when different voices and foundational discussions argue the key importance of the social dimension. This is the base of well-known positions in literature about action-research (Reason & Bradbury, 2008), transdisciplinarity (Pohl, 2017) or more recent phenomena like citizen science (Bonnesy et al., 2014). Moreover, social impact of research in different dimensions it's also at behind transnational and institutional movements connecting research activity with the Sustainable

Development Goals (SDG) or with Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles. SDG are a collection of 17 global goals set by the United Nations³ for addressing urgent issues like poverty, education, gender equality, energy, environment or social justice, among others (Griggs et al., 2013), which has derived also recently in specific recommendations and strategies for universities (SDSN Australia/Pacific, 2017). On the other hand, RRI⁴ is a multidisciplinary approach promoting the involvement of stakeholders and civil society in scientific activities for developing more inclusive innovation processes (Owen et al., 2012). That is, considering its social impact to foster civic engagement with the architectural features of technology-driven innovation and scientific activity (Ribeiro et al., 2016).

Although there is scarce academic literature about strategic planning connected to the issues mentioned above, some studies cover how it has gained some popularity in the general operation of universities (Holliman et al., 2015; Srinivasa et al., 2015; Dooris, 2004), also with openness and participative approaches (Amrollahi & Rowlands, 2017). More specific studies about the application of strategic thinking in research cover how it has been implemented in R&D processes in firms (Bemelmans, 1979), in aeronautic research (Burke et al., 1985), in research teams in the health sector (Leischow et al., 2008), in global initiatives of medical research (Berkley, 2010), in strategic collaboration within scientific centers (Arnold et al., 1998; Gray, 2008; Boardman & Gray, 2010), or in administrative management of research (Drummond, 2003).

Interesting case studies about achieving more collaborative and participative consensus for strategically planned research agendas cover how to combine online tools and offline sessions during the process (Wilbon, 2012), or how to engage iteratively different academic communities of practice around research strategic planning (Best et al., 2015). Sá and Tamtik (2012), on the other hand, point to the diversity of approaches and perceptions from academics about the research mission, usually constrained by the broader social and organizational structures of universities and the complex nature of the research enterprise.

2.2 Inspiring principles and examples

Following principles and practices of participatory design (Spinuzzi, 2005), as well as the need to combine different methods for effective strategic planning (Wilson,

³ More info:: <http://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/>

⁴ More info: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Responsible_Research_and_Innovation

1994), Dimmons approach sequenced the organic and iterative development of the process inspired by the four visual stages of a strategic plan as defined by Eppler & Platts (2009): Analysis, Development, Planning and Implementation (see Figure 1). This approach to co-design was based on the evidence of the importance of design features and social mechanisms for strategic planning success (Barzelay & Jacobsen, 2009), as well as decentralised approaches for higher engagement and performance in dynamic environments (Andersen, 2004). Aimed at benefiting from design thinking methodologies that have proven to improve participant engagement in research (Senabre et al., 2018), the process established different visual techniques at each stage needed for effective participation in a cross-disciplinary context.

Figure 1: Sequence based on the framework for visual strategizing of Eppler and Platts (2009)

Another inspirational principle has been the concept of participation as ecosystem (Fuster-Morell, 2010), considering Dimmons as a “research ecosystem” which holds several forms and degrees of involvement. During the process, it has been the leading concept for several degrees and forms of involvement, in order to take advantage of an ecosystemic approach.

Besides the mentioned references for benchmarking the group’s strategic objectives (IN3, UOC, SDG and RRI), for this collaborative exercise of long-term strategic planning, examples of inspiration in the academic and practitioner context were:

- University of South Florida Strategic Research Plan 2017-2021:
<http://www.usf.edu/research-innovation/documents/about-usfri/research-strategic-plan.pdf>
- Polytechnique Montréal strategic plan for research and innovation 2011-2016:
http://www.polymtl.ca/recherche/doc/Planstrategiquesansannexes_ANGL.pdf
- McGill University Strategic Research Plan 2013-18:
<https://www.mcgill.ca/research/about/srp>
- Brown University Strategic Research Plan 2016-2021:
<https://www.brown.edu/research/conducting-research-brown/about-office/strategic-plan>
- University Of British Columbia - Okanagan Strategic Research Plan 2009-2015:
<https://strategicplan.ubc.ca/the-plan/research-excellence/>

Beyond academic strategic planning, we can also point to innovation in strategic thinking in other type of organizations. In this regard the collaborative and sharing economy fields, area of expertise of Dimmons, are particularly rich. Creative strategic planning have a paradigmatic case in Wikipedia, involving one of the larger online communities in a commons process of collaborative planning, or in Shareable and its wide consultation and feedback process around the publication's strategy.

- Wikimedia Strategy 2015-2030:
https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Strategy/Wikimedia_movement/2017
- Shareable Strategic Plan 2017-2019:
<https://www.shareable.net/blog/a-new-path-for-shareable>

2.3 Methods and steps of the co-created planning

As mentioned above, the strategic planning of Dimmons has been shaped taking into consideration several reference frameworks. On the one hand, the immediate University context hosting Dimmons, that is, taking into account the strategic planning of IN3 and the broader one of UOC. On the other hand, as referenced in the introduction, matching and contrasting its different strategic objectives with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles, also references for a positive evolution of research.

Departing from the methodological framework developed by Eppler & Platts (2009), but adapting it to a co-creation sequence that also had as guiding principle several co-creation principles (Sanders & Stappers, 2008), the sequence followed during the

process of the strategic planning was the following one (described for each area in the following sections of this document) which comprised 3 co-creation sessions, 3 core team meetings and 2 online surveys:

Area	Method	Channel	Participants
Research agenda	Lightning talks	Offline meeting	First co-creation session: Core team + Community members (16 people)
Research approaches	DIY accreditations	Offline meeting	
Areas of interest in research	Lightning talks + Tagcloud	Offline meeting & Online	
Methodological orientations	Dotmocracy	Offline meeting	
Competitive analysis	Shared document	Online	Core team (2 people)
Dimmons mission and guiding principles	Survey #1 + Discussed edition	Online & Offline meeting	Second co-creation session: Core team + Community members (10 people)
Map of the ecosystem	Diagram + Survey #2	Offline meeting & Online	
SWOT analysis	Survey #2 + Card clustering	Offline meeting & Online	
Strategic objectives	Brainstorming + Shared document	Online	Core team (4 people)
Actions and key performance indicators (KPI)	Shared document + Survey #3 (for prioritisation & validation)	Offline meeting & Online	Core team + Community members (10 people)
Roadmap and yearly planning	Shared document + paper timeline	Offline meeting & Online	Third co-creation session: Core team + Community members (8 people)

The first co-creation session via different participative design techniques focused on mapping affinities and sensitivities, experience in methods and research approaches (visualizing methodological affinities) as well as personal interests of research, via different methods for eliciting and discussing contributions from participants. All the data generated during this first analysis stage of the strategic planning, concerning the group composition, allowed on the one hand to identify and map clearly opinions, basic assumptions and implicit understandings that needed to be surfaced, and on the other one to initiate the co-creation of the strategic planning with enough openness and implication of participants.

Different moments and materials used for the workshop sessions with the research team

That first session was followed by a survey among the core team and different collaborators of the group (Dimmons Community) where they could contribute prior to the second co-creation session providing information from their perspectives and points of view about connections in the ecosystem, desired elements for the group's mission and guiding principles, and suggest points related to its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats.

The second co-creation session departed from the first survey results in order to engage in a broader discussion about the mission and guiding principles, which were

discussed and re-edited offline during the debate. That second session also adopted a card sorting technique for clustering the survey results about strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats and identify and discuss the main ones. Finally, a first version of the map of Dimmons ecosystem was also drafted and discussed in that session.

The second survey took place once there was a first draft of strategic goals and actions generated by the core team via several meetings and online iterations. They were the base for an online poll that invited the broader network of collaborators to identify priorities, comment and validate the strategic goals and related actions in each case.

Finally, a third co-creation session to discuss the general outputs of the strategic planning, discuss and confirm the sequenced planning of actions until 2023 as a roadmap. This way, after combining at the methodological level offline co-design sessions with online surveys and discussions, the results of the process can be integrated to the group's day-to-day operations in order to align the strategic objectives and derived goals with the Agile management of tasks, adopted by the group since its beginning. This requirement had to do with the need to connect during the implementation phase the strategic plans with managerial practices (Poister, 2010).

3. Dimmons co-designed strategic planning

Reflecting the structure of some of the examples and references from the review on the state of the art of research strategic planning, the strategic plan of Dimmons has been developed in accordance with the following elements, which in different order were addressed in the described overlapping co-creation stages:

DEPARTING POINTS:

- Dimmons Mission
- Guiding principles
- Research agenda
- Group composition
- Methodological approaches
- Map of the ecosystem
- Coordination and routines

COMPETITIVE AND SWOT ANALYSES:

- Competitive analysis
- SWOT analysis

STRATEGIC PLANNING:

- Strategic objectives & goals
- Key performance indicators (KPI)
- Action plan for next 5 years

3.1 Departing points

Dimmons mission

«Fostering socioeconomic innovation through research, methodological experimentation and action for a commons oriented society»

Guiding principles

Dimmons guiding principles include: Research excellence and quality, Action orientation, Transdisciplinarity, Methodological pluralism and experimentation, Open knowledge, Transparency, Knowledge co-creation, and Glocalism.

Research excellence and quality: High research performance, talent, and rigor.

Action oriented: Oriented to **impact action and advance change** in the resolution of **social challenges** and taking advances of societies opportunities.

- Research to inform and improve the design of organizational processes, economic models, policies, legal frames and technology.
- Aiming at economic impact of research, favouring the exploration of results and a system transition towards an economy that puts people in the center.
- Promoting an empowering and sustainable relation with technology.

Transdisciplinary to tackle challenges and opportunities from diverse perspectives.

- **Mission oriented research** more than method or disciplinary oriented.
- Considering socioeconomic, gender, environmental **perspectives**.

Methodological pluralism and experimentation: Intensive use of cocreation, collaborative, visual and data oriented methods. **Research management innovation:** exploring agile methods, mutual care and gender dynamics, among others.

Open knowledge

- Lean approach, reproducibility and multi targets communication.
- 100% publications in **open access**.
- Publication of **open data** and research toolkits.

Transparency: Public, transparent and accountable processes regarding partners, impact and sources of funding.

Knowledge co-creation: Openness as part of a co-creation ecosystem (versus closed group “Ivory tower style”).

- Favoring an ecosystem of **plural modes of engagement**.
- Intense effort dedicated to disseminate and **create relations and feed community building** (meetings, collaborations, events).
- Collaborations with civil society, policy makers, economic actors and other research institutions.

Glocal: Global and local alliances, perspective and links to Barcelona, Catalonia and internationally.

Research agenda

The Dimmons group research is focus on socio economic innovation connected to the challenges and opportunities open up by the digital revolution sphere, and more concretely, on collaborative economy and the commons. Other terms adopted on certain occasions to refer to these topics are social innovation, common based peer production (CBPP), platform/open cooperativism, or sharing economy. These phenomena are approached from three perspectives:

- **Economics:** Emergence and economic implications of collaborative production, the configuration of a new production model based on open knowledge, level of economic activity and business models.
- **Public policies:** Policy co-creation and political innovation in emerging areas of public policy, and conflict and social mobilization associated with the regulations of socio economic innovation.
- **Methodological innovations and future studies:** Open science and methodological innovation emerging from collaborative economy applied to research and other ambits. Governance dilemmas and potential scenarios linked to highly innovative frontiers opened up by technological development.

Group composition

Dimmons is conceived as an ecosystem with diverse forms and degrees of involvement. This approach aims to embrace the findings on the presence of a “power law dynamic” (1/9/90) present in collaborative production (Fuster-Morell, 2010).

Dimmons composition is organized by circles of involvement:

- **Core Team:** Those with a substantial contractual relation with the group, and/or working regularly from Dimmons office. Director, postdocs and PhDs with grant.
- **Dimmons Community:** Composed by Dimmons PhDs, and collaborators (such as professors from UOC studies, former visitors, researchers of other groups or experts and practitioners on Dimmons areas engaged with Dimmons research).
- **Dimmons quadruple helix/ecosystem:** Set of further relations of collaboration, target impact or audience. Which will be presented in the “Map of the ecosystem” section.

Mapping group attitudes, research interest and methodological orientation

With this “bottom-up” approach based on surveys and co-creation sessions core and community members were targeted. After a first stage for recognition and initial contact between the core team of Dimmons and its main group of collaborators (researchers of other groups and studies, PhDs candidates, visiting scholars, practitioners, etc) the process focused on mapping affinities and sensitivities, experience in methods and research approaches (visualizing methodological affinities) as well as personal interests of research, which took place in a round of “lightning talks” during the first workshop.

Research approaches

One of the first steps of the new Dimmons strategic planning was to identify what are the commonalities in relation to personal attitudes and perceived strengths of the members of the group, as well as the wider network of collaborators. During a first workshop meeting, each participant selected the three attitudes and strengths that perceived more related to him or her, with also the possibility to create new “tags” defining how they are (see Figure 1). This allowed to identify how the majority has an attitude towards action-research, giving importance to communication, and are characterised by exploration or intuitiveness in the way they work. Traditional categorization of researchers such as by methods (qualitative or quantitative oriented) or by disciplines is not as present in Dimmons team.

Figure 1: Dimmons research approaches

Areas of interest in research

Traditionally to the methodological and topic shared interests and expertise described above, the content analysis (Figure 2) of the different presentations of the group members and collaborators allowed to identify commonalities as well as to discover shared areas of interest. From social and people-centric views of the scientific activity and impact, to issues of transformation or economic processes, and its relation to economy, media, policies and in a broader sense the political domain.

Figure 2: Tagcloud generated after content analysis of the introductions of group members

Methodological orientation

Another key aspect for developing the strategic planning has been to initially identify the different interests to research methods and approaches within the wider scale of collaborators of the Dimmon group. Ranging from more qualitative to more quantitative methods, as well as wider fields of research, results showed a relevant expertise with interviews and observational methods, while less members of the group were used to apply quantitative approaches such as surveys or lab experiments (Figure 3). On the other hand, approaches like action-research, desk research or co-design were very familiar for a relevant percentage of the group composition.

Figure 3: Experience with research methods and approaches

Although not exhaustive, these first visualizations allowed to identify later on in the strategic planning process areas of improvement and implications for the group composition in the mid and long term.

Strategic diagnosis (SWOT analysis)

The analysis of the internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats of the Dimmons group, was conducted in between the analysis and development stages of the strategic planning. First, eliciting about the different SWOT elements via an online survey, and during a second workshop clustering and discussing the results among all participants. This allowed to have a divergence moment where a considerable number of factors were generated, and then a second one of intense convergence and synthesis where the main ones were identified and given a specific category.

Dimmons SWOT	FAVOURABLE	UNFAVOURABLE
I N T E R N A L	Strengths: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Multidisciplinary focus 2. Cutting-edge approach 3. Transversal impact 4. High motivation 5. Open experimentation 6. Wide reputation 	Weaknesses: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Early stage of the group 2. Complexity of action approach 3. Team dispersion 4. Ineffective departmental relationships
E X T E R N A L	Opportunities: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Commons "momentum" 2. Interest from stakeholders 3. Transformation of research for impact 4. Barcelona context 5. New streams for funding 	Threats: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rigid university frameworks 2. Unstable topic background 3. Complexities of applying for funding 4. Changing political agendas 5. High demand pressure

Table summarising the main SWOT elements identified in relation to Dimmons.

The analysis required also internal meetings of the "core" participants of the group to process the information generated so far, then sharing summary documents to make sure the rest of participants validated the results and had a second chance to inform the process and provide feedback about it.

3.3 Strategic plan

Six strategic objectives for 2018-2023

After the identification of potential strategic objectives connected to the SWOT analysis and rest of knowledge co-generated around the research group, through a series of iterations and a survey there was a definition and prioritization of the following strategic objectives:

O1: REFERENCE PUBLICATIONS - Generate a high-quality research corpus of theoretical framework on socio-economic innovation

Actions derived from this strategic objective have to do with publishing on top academic journals (specially open access) but also participation in conferences or supporting alternative publications with rigorous content. To become a reference in the field though original and high level generated expertise.

O2: OPEN TOOLS - Contribute to processes in action for the resolution of social challenges by developing research-based resources

Generate practical open content (data, etc) and open source tools (toolkits, tutorials, indicators, apps, etc) that can have impact beyond academic community, and favor exploitation of results with actions in the field.

O3: ECOSYSTEM BUILDING - Consolidate a glocal network of partner organizations for quadruple helix collaboration to favour social impact and resilience

To reinforce wide alliances with cities and public policy innovation, as well as other economic actors, with activities and events to generate change as well as practical knowledge.

O4: EMPOWERED TEAM - Consolidate the team with complementary backgrounds, healthy environment and gender-balanced talent

Actions for new and talented scholarships or academic stays the group, and also to agreements with new members expert in complementary fields, as well as actions for a healthy work environment and mutual care, or an internal gender balance.

O5: CATALYTIC SUSTAINABILITY - Obtain funding for action-research from competitive calls with high impact and visibility

Create a diverse and resilient funding scheme. Applying to EU calls or other public funding, to local programs or alliances where we get resources by providing research services.

O6: UNIVERSITY SHIFT - Engage with open access, Commonification processes, transdisciplinarity, Agile and other changing paradigms in the academic culture

Actions oriented to "hack" the academic process from within (specially improving institutional processes and performance), but also experimenting with civic participation in science and responsible research and innovation (RRI).

Actions and key performance indicators (KPI)

Finally, for this first version of the strategic plan of the research group and planning stage, the different actions derived from each objective and its corresponding key performance indicators are summarised in this section.

For reaching them, there was a first session with the direction of Dimmons and afterwards an open document to reflect ideal scenarios and potential actions derived from them, all related to the previous analyses. This was followed by a second survey to validate and highlight those objectives and actions that had more support from the team and collaborators around the group.

Dimmons strategic objective	Actions	Indicators
O1: REFERENCE PUBLICATIONS 	O1.1 Increase in scientific production	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Indexed articles for IP (ISI), postdocs and PhD candidates (per year) 2. Publications in Quartiles 1-4 (for same categories) 3. Book chapters and books (publishers with impact)
	O1.2 Useful resources to streamline paper publications	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Internal resource for sprint writing, reviewing and submitting papers 2. Shared database for journals and conferences 3. Index of papers under preparation
	O1.3 Series of internal/external seminars	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Doctor Dimmons seminars 2. Annual conference (Procomuns)
	O1.4 Active participation in international academic networks	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conferences participating as paper givers or keynotes 2. Posters in conferences 3. Membership as peer-reviewers in publications 4. Memberships of academic boards of projects / journals

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Not attendance to conference as mere participants
	<p>O1.5 Responsive research agenda for aligning theory with new tendencies</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Search report on queries to Google and other tools about tendencies 2. Collaborations with experts and practitioners in other fields
<p>O2: OPEN TOOLS</p>	<p>O2.1 Communication plan and new Dimmons website platform as repository in accordance with the strategic plan</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dimmons communication strategy plan 2. Improved features of Dimmons website 3. Visit metrics of the website
	<p>O2.2 Replicable and tested toolkit for digital platforms and policy co-creation</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Beta version of the toolkit Col·lacy for digital platforms 2. Beta version of the toolkit for policy co-creation 3. Translated versions to English, Spanish, Catalan 4. Downloads from the Dimmons repository and mentions in Social Media 5. Documented use by other researchers, entrepreneurs and policy-related practitioners
	<p>O2.3 Data commons platform for open research and visualizations on collaborative economy</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. MVP of the data commons platform in use 2. Beta version of the data commons platform 3. Visit metrics of the platform 4. Data packages contributed by other organisations 5. Publications about the visualizations generated (from Dimmons or other groups)
	<p>O2.4 Alternative indicators to research</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Manifesto for action-research impact metrics 2. Shared guidelines for alternative indicators

	metrics, for social impact of the group	3. Report about social impact of Dimmons based on the shared guidelines
O3: ECOSYSTEM BUILDING 	O3.1 Projection and creation of policy-related links with cities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organisation of Sharing cities meeting 2. Number of agreements or formal alliances with cities
	O3.2 Training track for co-creation & action-research facilitation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Learning materials generated (for UOC or other projects) 2. Courses online about the topic 3. Offline workshops about the project
	O3.3 Dimmons dissemination and media outreach plan	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Communication plan focused on media outreach and advocacy
	O3.4 Master at UOC about collaborative economy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Materials generated for the Master 2. Number of students 3. Experts and organizations collaborating
	O3.5 Shared network agenda for contacts and alliances	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. MVP application of the agenda tool
	O3.6 Closer relation at local level with Generalitat	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Meetings with representatives 2. Projects derived from connecting
	O3.7 Wider intellectual dialogue at local level with other disciplines	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Events attended from other organisations or agents 2. Events organised with other organisations or agents
O4: CATALYTIC SUSTAINABILITY	O4.1 Strategic competitive proposals and research agreements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. IP-oriented funding programs (ERC, ICREA) 2. European funded proposals

	and contracts	
	O4.2 Participation in review committees of EU projects	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. EU funded projects with Dimmons as advisors 2. Meetings in Brussels / online for new calls
	O4.3 Strong relation with organization as partners in East Europe	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of an East Europe partner 2. Organizations collaborating 3. Projects in common since collaboration
	O4.4 Cooperativist-oriented spinoff of Dimmons activity	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Viability plan of the spin-off 2. MVP of the service for initial activity 3. Funding derived from activity
	O4.5 Protocol for sharing funds and resources with other organisations	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Defined position of Dimmons in the ecosystem and protocol of monetary relations (when accept retribution from collaborations) 2. Directory of pilots and other collaborations funded via Dimmons
O5: EMPOWERED TEAM 	O5.1 Presenting proposals for attracting talent in competitive competitions of prestige and curricular valorisation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. IP accreditation processes 2. New PhD candidates joining Dimmons with own funding 3. Postdoc winning by Dimmons PhDs 4. Presentation of proposal to join Dimmons by international researchers
	O5.2 Pool of profiles and other resources for detecting and attracting talent	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared directory with collaborators and potential candidates 2. New members of the group, part-time or full-time
	O5.3 Added talent in specific positions for	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. New data analysis / development expert 2. New economics / statistical expert

	the group	3. Projects related to data analysis and development
	O5.4 Improved capacity for organisation of events and sessions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared “howto” document for practical guidelines 2. Survey for participants in Dimmons events
	O5.5 Team consolidation and Dimmons community	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Workplan “core” team 2. Dimmons community meetings (Grup Recerca Emergent)
	O5.6 Established Dimmons Gender action plan	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Defined Dimmons Equality Plan 2. Internal application and testing of a pilot resource plan
	O5.7 Agenda of celebrations related to achievements and open activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared tool for transversal information about dates and goals 2. Internal events and celebrations
	O5.8 Program of skill and expert development for group members	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Individual courses for expanding skills and background of the team 2. Collective learning experiences as team
	O5.9 Shared resource for welcoming and common knowledge	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Welcome kit to Dimmons with practical info
	O5.10 Protocols for research reflection and respectful convivence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared resource and agreement for personal paces 2. Internal survey for work satisfaction

	O5.11 Code for ethics behaviour and technological sovereignty	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared guidelines for ethical professional and action-research integrity 2. Shared guidelines for technological sovereignty within the group 3. Migrations to open source and ethical tools for regular activity
<p>O6: UNIVERSITY SHIFT</p>	O6.1 Strategic planning, with a co-created methodology	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Published strategic plan 2018-2023 incorporating feedback 2. Academic paper about the process
	O6.2 System of indicators about research and management of the group to track and achieve the strategic planning	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Metrics of performance in Kanboard
	O6.3 Reduction of time dedicated to management and frustration with research services	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Internal "HowTo" document with useful protocols 2. Research assistant position (part-time) 3. Proposals of improvement and critics of functionalities
	O6.4 Interdisciplinary activities with technology-oriented research groups	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared action or initiative with a IT-related group, from UOC or external
	O6.5 Methodological experimentation & design of new co-creation methods	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Documented sessions for co-designing methods and materials 2. Tested methods and materials 3. Paper about the meta-process

	<p>O6.6 New appropriated formats as channels of publication and research dissemination</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Events related to new formats and channels for research culture 2. MVP publication of P2P citizen science journal 3. MVP of art and performance communication of science
	<p>O6.7 Amplified expertise in post-normal and future studies</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Events related to the field 2. Publications connecting with the theoretical framework
	<p>O6.8 Joined forces with civic processes to foster knowledge shifts between academia-society</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Documented meetings and events with civil society actors 2. Publication about the process 3. Campaign in favor of open knowledge

5. References

- Ahlstrand, B., Lampel, J., & Mintzberg, H. (2001). *Strategy Safari: A Guided Tour Through The Wilds of Strategic Management*. Simon and Schuster.
- Amrollahi, A., & Rowlands, B. (2017). Collaborative open strategic planning: a method and case study. *Information Technology & People, 30*(4), 832-852.
- Andersen, T. J. (2004). Integrating decentralized strategy making and strategic planning processes in dynamic environments. *Journal of management studies, 41*(8), 1271-1299.
- Arnold, E., Rush, H., Bessant, J., & Hobday, M. (1998). Strategic planning in research and technology institutes. *R&D Management, 28*(2), 89-100.
- Barzelay, M., & Jacobsen, A. S. (2009). Theorizing implementation of public management policy reforms: A case study of strategic planning and programming in the European Commission. *Governance, 22*(2), 319-334.
- Bemelmans, T. (1979). Strategic planning for research and development. *Long Range Planning, 12*(2), 33-44.
- Berkley, S., Bertram, K., Delfraissy, J. F., Draghia-Akli, R., Fauci, A., Hallenbeck, C., ... & Piot, P. (2010). The 2010 scientific strategic plan of the Global HIV Vaccine Enterprise. *Nature medicine, 16*(9), 981.
- Best, K. M., Jarrín, O., Bутtenheim, A. M., Bowles, K. H., & Curley, M. A. (2015). Innovation in creating a strategic plan for research within an academic community. *Nursing outlook, 63*(4), 456-461.
- Binswanger, M. (2014). Excellence by Nonsense: The Competition for Publications in Modern Science. In *Opening Science* (pp. 49-72). Springer, Cham.
- Boardman, C., & Gray, D. (2010). The new science and engineering management: cooperative research centers as government policies, industry strategies, and organizations. *The Journal of Technology Transfer, 35*(5), 445-459.
- Bonney, R., Shirk, J. L., Phillips, T. B., Wiggins, A., Ballard, H. L., Miller-Rushing, A. J., & Parrish, J. K. (2014). Next steps for citizen science. *Science, 343*(6178), 1436-1437.
- Burke, W. W., Richley, E. A., & DeAngelis, L. (1985). Changing leadership and planning processes at the Lewis Research Center, National Aeronautics and Space Administration. *Human Resource Management, 24*(1), 81-90.

-
- Carayannis, E. G., & Campbell, D. F. (2012). Mode 3 knowledge production in quadruple helix innovation systems. In *Mode 3 Knowledge Production in Quadruple Helix Innovation Systems* (pp. 1-63). Springer, New York, NY.
- Derrick, G., & Alicen Nickson, M. A. (2014). Invisible intermediaries: A systematic review into the role of research management in university and institutional research processes. *Journal of Research Administration*, 45(2), 11.
- Dooris, M. J., Kelley, J. M., & Trainer, J. F. (2004). Strategic planning in higher education. *New Directions for Institutional Research*, 2004(123), 5-11.
- Drummond, C. N. (2003). Strategic planning for research administration. *Journal of Research Administration*, 34(2), 4.
- Eppler, M. J., & Platts, K. W. (2009). Visual strategizing: the systematic use of visualization in the strategic-planning process. *Long Range Planning*, 42(1), 42-74.
- Fuster-Morell, M. (2010). *Governance of online creation communities: Provision of infrastructure for the building of digital commons* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Gibbons, M., Limoges, C., Nowotny, H., Schwartzman, S., Scott, P., & Trow, M. (1994). *The new production of knowledge: The dynamics of science and research in contemporary societies*. Sage.
- Gray, D. O. (2008). Making team science better: Applying improvement-oriented evaluation principles to evaluation of cooperative research centers. *New Directions for Evaluation*, 2008(118), 73-87.
- Holliman, Richard; Adams, Anne; Blackman, Tim; Collins, Trevor; Davies, Gareth; Dibb, Sally; Grand, Ann; Holti, Richard; McKerlie, Fiona; Mahony, Nick and Wissenburg, Astrid eds. (2015). *An Open Research University*. Milton Keynes: The Open University.
- Jasanoff, S. (2003). Technologies of humility: citizen participation in governing science. *Minerva*, 41(3), 223-244.
- Leischow, S. J., Best, A., Trochim, W. M., Clark, P. I., Gallagher, R. S., Marcus, S. E., & Matthews, E. (2008). Systems thinking to improve the public's health. *American journal of preventive medicine*, 35(2), S196-S203.
- Ordorika, I., & Lloyd, M. (2015). International rankings and the contest for university hegemony. *Journal of Education Policy*, 30(3), 385-405.
- Owen, R., Macnaghten, P., & Stilgoe, J. (2012). Responsible research and innovation: From science in society to science for society, with society. *Science and public policy*, 39(6), 751-760.
- Pohl, C., Krütli, P., & Stauffacher, M. (2017). Ten reflective steps for rendering research societally relevant. *GAIA-Ecological Perspectives for Science and Society*, 26(1), 43-51.

-
- Poister, T. H. (2010). The future of strategic planning in the public sector: Linking strategic management and performance. *Public Administration Review*, 70(s1).
- Reason, P., & Bradbury, H. (Eds.). (2008). *Handbook of action research: Participative inquiry and practice*. Sage.
- Ribeiro, B. E., Smith, R. D., & Millar, K. (2016). A Mobilising Concept? Unpacking Academic Representations of Responsible Research and Innovation. *Science and engineering ethics*, 1-23.
- Sá, C. M., & Tamtik, M. (2012). Strategic planning for academic research. *Higher Education Management and Policy*, 24(1), 1-20.
- Scheliga, K., & Friesike, S. (2014). Putting open science into practice: A social dilemma?. *First Monday*, 19(9).
- Schildhauer, T., & Voss, H. (2014). Open innovation and crowdsourcing in the sciences. In *Opening Science* (pp. 255-269). Springer, Cham.
- SDSN Australia/Pacific (2017): Getting started with the SDGs in universities: A guide for universities, higher education institutions, and the academic sector. Australia, New Zealand and Pacific Edition. Sustainable Development Solutions Network – Australia/Pacific, Melbourne.
- Sanders, E., and Stappers, P. J. (2008). 'Co-creation and the new landscapes of design'. *Co-design* 4(1), pp. 5-18.
- Senabre, E., Ferran-Ferrer, N., & Perelló, J. (2018). Participatory design of citizen science experiments. *Comunicar*, 26(54), 29-38.
- Sidler, M. (2014). Open Science and the Three Cultures: Expanding Open Science to all Domains of Knowledge Creation. In *Opening Science* (pp. 81-85). Springer, Cham.
- Spinuzzi, C. (2005). The methodology of participatory design. *Technical communication*, 52(2), 163-174.
- Srinivasa Rao, A. B., Kumar, P. M., & Aithal, P. S. (2015). Strategic Planning in Higher Education Institutions: A Case Study of SIMS-VISION 2025.
- Vom Brocke, J., & Lippe, S. (2015). Managing collaborative research projects: A synthesis of project management literature and directives for future research. *International Journal of Project Management*, 33(5), 1022-1039.
- Wang, J., & Hicks, D. (2015). Scientific teams: Self-assembly, fluidness, and interdependence. *Journal of Informetrics*, 9(1), 197-207.
- Wilbon, A. D. (2012). Interactive planning for strategy development in academic-based cooperative research enterprises. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 24(1), 89-105.
- Wilson, I. (1994). Strategic planning isn't dead—it changed. *Long range planning*, 27(4), 12-24.

Dimmons.net Research Group

STRATEGIC PLANNING 2018-2023

Extended Version 1.0 - April 2018

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1. Introduction

Created in January 2016, Dimmons.net is one of the ten research groups of the Internet Interdisciplinary Institute (IN3), a research center of the Open University of Catalonia (UOC). Dimmons group research focuses on socio economic innovation connected to digital technologies, and more concretely, on the collaborative economy and the Commons.

This is a report of the strategic planning process of Dimmons, which has been developed adopting a co-designed approach. Involving the diversity of its group's members and network of close collaborators, as well as other representative stakeholders, the goal has been to establish the strategic objectives for the research group from 2018 to 2023. This strategic planning of Dimmons follows the previous strategic planning of the IN3¹ and the UOC in 2016².

The development of the co-designed process, as well as this report, has been guided by Mayo Fuster (Dimmons's director) and it's part of a case study developed for the PhD project of Enric Senabre on co-creation methodologies applied to research innovation. In this sense the design of Dimmons, and this strategic planning, could be conceived as a meta-research process. As a process of design and implementation of a research group in order to tackle and reflect on: *"What are the organizational logics and strategies that favor the impact and resilience of research groups in a context of profound changes due to the transition to the Knowledge Society?"*. We developed this approach as an action-research looking for inspiration in the the precise area we are expert on: collaborative production. Thus, a secondary meta-research questions is: *"How far methodological innovations on collaborative production could provide guidelines and solutions to design resilient and successful research groups today?"*.

The organization of this report is twofold: First, a chapter presenting the state of the art on strategic planning for research and its connection with key issues in open science and transdisciplinarity, as well as an explanation of the methodology adopted. Secondly, a sequenced description of the strategic planning outputs, from the departing points of the group to the collaborative analysis, followed by the establishment of strategies around the agreed common goals.

¹ URL: <https://www.uoc.edu/portal/en/in3/coneix/pla-estrategic/index.htm>

² URL: <http://www.uoc.edu/portal/en/universitat/pla-estrategic/index.html>

2. State of the art, inspiration and methodological approach

2.1 State of the art on strategic planning for research

Despite the current competition between academic institutions for resources and prestige adopting evaluation systems, ranking mechanisms and performance indicators (Ordorika & Lloyd, 2015), there's little evidence on successful strategies and practices of research management (Derrick & Nickson, 2014). Specially when it comes to the additional need to adapt the production of scientific knowledge to collaborative and interdisciplinary approaches (Gibbons et al., 1994), in a context of networked academic organisations and researchers (Wang & Hicks, 2015) and the "participatory turn" of science (Jasanoff, 2003). In that sense, strategic planning seems one of the possible elements that can contribute to better management practices in scientific institutions (Wilbon, 2012), since collaborative practices in research need to balance flexibility with structured decision-making processes, as well as autonomy with shared long-term vision (Vom Brocke & Lippe, 2015).

This seems especially important in times of a needed merging in a Academia between Open Science approaches and wider Open Knowledge practices (Sidler, 2014), as well as the opportunity to explore dynamics of participative open innovation in research (Schildhauer & Voss, 2014). However, among the current challenges related to strategy and long term goals for scientific activity, we can find from individual and systemic obstacles for research openness (Scheliga & Friesike, 2014) to the recurrent crisis on the competition for impact factors and publication pressure (Binswanger, 2014). Beyond that, another relevant issue nowadays is the concept of scientific impact itself, when different voices and foundational discussions argue the key importance of the social dimension. This is the base of well-known positions in literature about action-research (Reason & Bradbury, 2008), transdisciplinarity (Pohl, 2017) or more recent phenomena like citizen science (Bonnesy et al., 2014). Moreover, social impact of research in different dimensions it's also at behind transnational and institutional movements connecting research activity with the Sustainable

Development Goals (SDG) or with Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles. SDG are a collection of 17 global goals set by the United Nations³ for addressing urgent issues like poverty, education, gender equality, energy, environment or social justice, among others (Griggs et al., 2013), which has derived also recently in specific recommendations and strategies for universities (SDSN Australia/Pacific, 2017). On the other hand, RRI⁴ is a multidisciplinary approach promoting the involvement of stakeholders and civil society in scientific activities for developing more inclusive innovation processes (Owen et al., 2012). That is, considering its social impact to foster civic engagement with the architectural features of technology-driven innovation and scientific activity (Ribeiro et al., 2016).

Although there is scarce academic literature about strategic planning connected to the issues mentioned above, some studies cover how it has gained some popularity in the general operation of universities (Holliman et al., 2015; Srinivasa et al., 2015; Dooris, 2004), also with openness and participative approaches (Amrollahi & Rowlands, 2017). More specific studies about the application of strategic thinking in research cover how it has been implemented in R&D processes in firms (Bemelmans, 1979), in aeronautic research (Burke et al., 1985), in research teams in the health sector (Leischow et al., 2008), in global initiatives of medical research (Berkley, 2010), in strategic collaboration within scientific centers (Arnold et al., 1998; Gray, 2008; Boardman & Gray, 2010), or in administrative management of research (Drummond, 2003).

Interesting case studies about achieving more collaborative and participative consensus for strategically planned research agendas cover how to combine online tools and offline sessions during the process (Wilbon, 2012), or how to engage iteratively different academic communities of practice around research strategic planning (Best et al., 2015). Sá and Tamtik (2012), on the other hand, point to the diversity of approaches and perceptions from academics about the research mission, usually constrained by the broader social and organizational structures of universities and the complex nature of the research enterprise.

2.2 Inspiring principles and examples

Following principles and practices of participatory design (Spinuzzi, 2005), as well as the need to combine different methods for effective strategic planning (Wilson,

³ More info:: <http://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/>

⁴ More info: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Responsible_Research_and_Innovation

1994), Dimmons approach sequenced the organic and iterative development of the process inspired by the four visual stages of a strategic plan as defined by Eppler & Platts (2009): Analysis, Development, Planning and Implementation (see Figure 1). This approach to co-design was based on the evidence of the importance of design features and social mechanisms for strategic planning success (Barzelay & Jacobsen, 2009), as well as decentralised approaches for higher engagement and performance in dynamic environments (Andersen, 2004). Aimed at benefiting from design thinking methodologies that have proven to improve participant engagement in research (Senabre et al., 2018), the process established different visual techniques at each stage needed for effective participation in a cross-disciplinary context.

Figure 1: Sequence based on the framework for visual strategizing of Eppler and Platts (2009)

Another inspirational principle has been the concept of participation as ecosystem (Fuster-Morell, 2010), considering Dimmons as a “research ecosystem” which holds several forms and degrees of involvement. During the process, it has been the leading concept for several degrees and forms of involvement, in order to take advantage of an ecosystemic approach.

Besides the mentioned references for benchmarking the group’s strategic objectives (IN3, UOC, SDG and RRI), for this collaborative exercise of long-term strategic planning, examples of inspiration in the academic and practitioner context were:

- University of South Florida Strategic Research Plan 2017-2021:
<http://www.usf.edu/research-innovation/documents/about-usfri/research-strategic-plan.pdf>
- Polytechnique Montréal strategic plan for research and innovation 2011-2016:
http://www.polymtl.ca/recherche/doc/Planstrategiquesansannexes_ANGL.pdf
- McGill University Strategic Research Plan 2013-18:
<https://www.mcgill.ca/research/about/srp>
- Brown University Strategic Research Plan 2016-2021:
<https://www.brown.edu/research/conducting-research-brown/about-office/strategic-plan>
- University Of British Columbia - Okanagan Strategic Research Plan 2009-2015:
<https://strategicplan.ubc.ca/the-plan/research-excellence/>

Beyond academic strategic planning, we can also point to innovation in strategic thinking in other type of organizations. In this regard the collaborative and sharing economy fields, area of expertise of Dimmons, are particularly rich. Creative strategic planning have a paradigmatic case in Wikipedia, involving one of the larger online communities in a commons process of collaborative planning, or in Shareable and its wide consultation and feedback process around the publication's strategy.

- Wikimedia Strategy 2015-2030:
https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Strategy/Wikimedia_movement/2017
- Shareable Strategic Plan 2017-2019:
<https://www.shareable.net/blog/a-new-path-for-shareable>

2.3 Methods and steps of the co-created planning

As mentioned above, the strategic planning of Dimmons has been shaped taking into consideration several reference frameworks. On the one hand, the immediate University context hosting Dimmons, that is, taking into account the strategic planning of IN3 and the broader one of UOC. On the other hand, as referenced in the introduction, matching and contrasting its different strategic objectives with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles, also references for a positive evolution of research.

Departing from the methodological framework developed by Eppler & Platts (2009), but adapting it to a co-creation sequence that also had as guiding principle several co-creation principles (Sanders & Stappers, 2008), the sequence followed during the

process of the strategic planning was the following one (described for each area in the following sections of this document) which comprised 3 co-creation sessions, 3 core team meetings and 2 online surveys:

Area	Method	Channel	Participants
Research agenda	Lightning talks	Offline meeting	First co-creation session: Core team + Community members (16 people)
Research approaches	DIY accreditations	Offline meeting	
Areas of interest in research	Lightning talks + Tagcloud	Offline meeting & Online	
Methodological orientations	Dotmocracy	Offline meeting	
Competitive analysis	Shared document	Online	Core team (2 people)
Dimmons mission and guiding principles	Survey #1 + Discussed edition	Online & Offline meeting	Second co-creation session: Core team + Community members (10 people)
Map of the ecosystem	Diagram + Survey #2	Offline meeting & Online	
SWOT analysis	Survey #2 + Card clustering	Offline meeting & Online	
Strategic objectives	Brainstorming + Shared document	Online	Core team (4 people)
Actions and key performance indicators (KPI)	Shared document + Survey #3 (for prioritisation & validation)	Offline meeting & Online	Core team + Community members (10 people)
Roadmap and yearly planning	Shared document + paper timeline	Offline meeting & Online	Third co-creation session: Core team + Community members (8 people)

The first co-creation session via different participative design techniques focused on mapping affinities and sensitivities, experience in methods and research approaches (visualizing methodological affinities) as well as personal interests of research, via different methods for eliciting and discussing contributions from participants. All the data generated during this first analysis stage of the strategic planning, concerning the group composition, allowed on the one hand to identify and map clearly opinions, basic assumptions and implicit understandings that needed to be surfaced, and on the other one to initiate the co-creation of the strategic planning with enough openness and implication of participants.

Different moments and materials used for the workshop sessions with the research team

That first session was followed by a survey among the core team and different collaborators of the group (Dimmons Community) where they could contribute prior to the second co-creation session providing information from their perspectives and points of view about connections in the ecosystem, desired elements for the group's mission and guiding principles, and suggest points related to its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats.

The second co-creation session departed from the first survey results in order to engage in a broader discussion about the mission and guiding principles, which were

discussed and re-edited offline during the debate. That second session also adopted a card sorting technique for clustering the survey results about strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats and identify and discuss the main ones. Finally, a first version of the map of Dimmons ecosystem was also drafted and discussed in that session.

The second survey took place once there was a first draft of strategic goals and actions generated by the core team via several meetings and online iterations. They were the base for an online poll that invited the broader network of collaborators to identify priorities, comment and validate the strategic goals and related actions in each case.

Finally, a third co-creation session to discuss the general outputs of the strategic planning, discuss and confirm the sequenced planning of actions until 2023 as a roadmap. This way, after combining at the methodological level offline co-design sessions with online surveys and discussions, the results of the process can be integrated to the group's day-to-day operations in order to align the strategic objectives and derived goals with the Agile management of tasks, adopted by the group since its beginning. This requirement had to do with the need to connect during the implementation phase the strategic plans with managerial practices (Poister, 2010).

3. Dimmons co-designed strategic planning

Reflecting the structure of some of the examples and references from the review on the state of the art of research strategic planning, the strategic plan of Dimmons has been developed in accordance with the following elements, which in different order were addressed in the described overlapping co-creation stages:

DEPARTING POINTS:

- Dimmons Mission
- Guiding principles
- Research agenda
- Group composition
- Methodological approaches
- Map of the ecosystem
- Coordination and routines

COMPETITIVE AND SWOT ANALYSES:

- Competitive analysis
- SWOT analysis

STRATEGIC PLANNING:

- Strategic objectives & goals
- Key performance indicators (KPI)
- Action plan for next 5 years

3.1 Departing points

Dimmons mission

«Fostering socioeconomic innovation through research, methodological experimentation and action for a commons oriented society»

Guiding principles

Dimmons guiding principles include: Research excellence and quality, Action orientation, Transdisciplinarity, Methodological pluralism and experimentation, Open knowledge, Transparency, Knowledge co-creation, and Glocalism.

Research excellence and quality: High research performance, talent, and rigor.

Action oriented: Oriented to **impact action and advance change** in the resolution of **social challenges** and taking advances of societies opportunities.

- Research to inform and improve the design of organizational processes, economic models, policies, legal frames and technology.
- Aiming at economic impact of research, favouring the exploration of results and a system transition towards an economy that puts people in the center.
- Promoting an empowering and sustainable relation with technology.

Transdisciplinary to tackle challenges and opportunities from diverse perspectives.

- **Mission oriented research** more than method or disciplinary oriented.
- Considering socioeconomic, gender, environmental **perspectives**.

Methodological pluralism and experimentation: Intensive use of cocreation, collaborative, visual and data oriented methods. **Research management innovation:** exploring agile methods, mutual care and gender dynamics, among others.

Open knowledge

- Lean approach, reproducibility and multi targets communication.
- 100% publications in **open access**.
- Publication of **open data** and research toolkits.

Transparency: Public, transparent and accountable processes regarding partners, impact and sources of funding.

Knowledge co-creation: Openness as part of a co-creation ecosystem (versus closed group “Ivory tower style”).

- Favoring an ecosystem of **plural modes of engagement**.
- Intense effort dedicated to disseminate and **create relations and feed community building** (meetings, collaborations, events).
- Collaborations with civil society, policy makers, economic actors and other research institutions.

Glocal: Global and local alliances, perspective and links to Barcelona, Catalonia and internationally.

Research agenda

The Dimmons group research is focus on socio economic innovation connected to the challenges and opportunities open up by the digital revolution sphere, and more concretely, on collaborative economy and the commons. Other terms adopted on certain occasions to refer to these topics are social innovation, common based peer production (CBPP), platform/open cooperativism, or sharing economy. These phenomena are approached from three perspectives:

- **Economics:** Emergence and economic implications of collaborative production, the configuration of a new production model based on open knowledge, level of economic activity and business models.
- **Public policies:** Policy co-creation and political innovation in emerging areas of public policy, and conflict and social mobilization associated with the regulations of socio economic innovation.
- **Methodological innovations and future studies:** Open science and methodological innovation emerging from collaborative economy applied to research and other ambits. Governance dilemmas and potential scenarios linked to highly innovative frontiers opened up by technological development.

Group composition

Dimmons is conceived as an ecosystem with diverse forms and degrees of involvement. This approach aims to embrace the findings on the presence of a “power law dynamic” (1/9/90) present in collaborative production (Fuster-Morell, 2010).

Dimmons composition is organized by circles of involvement:

- **Core Team:** Those with a substantial contractual relation with the group, and/or working regularly from Dimmons office. Director, postdocs and PhDs with grant.
- **Dimmons Community:** Composed by Dimmons PhDs, and collaborators (such as professors from UOC studies, former visitors, researchers of other groups or experts and practitioners on Dimmons areas engaged with Dimmons research).
- **Dimmons quadruple helix/ecosystem:** Set of further relations of collaboration, target impact or audience. Which will be presented in the “Map of the ecosystem” section.

Mapping group attitudes, research interest and methodological orientation

With this “bottom-up” approach based on surveys and co-creation sessions core and community members were target. After a first stage for recognition and initial contact between the core team of Dimmons and its main group of collaborators (researchers of other groups and studies, PhDs candidates, visiting scholars, practitioners, etc) the process focused on mapping affinities and sensitivities, experience in methods and research approaches (visualizing methodological affinities) as well as personal interests of research, which took place in a round of “lightning talks” during the first workshop.

Research approaches

One of the first steps of the new Dimmons strategic planning was to identify what are the commonalities in relation to personal attitudes and perceived strengths of the members of the group, as well as the wider network of collaborators. During a first workshop meeting, each participant selected the three attitudes and strengths that perceived more related to him or her, with also the possibility to create new “tags” defining how they are (see Figure 1). This allowed to identify how the majority has an attitude towards action-research, giving importance to communication, and are characterised by exploration or intuitiveness in the way they work. Traditional categorization of researchers such as by methods (qualitative or quantitative oriented) or by disciplines is not as present in Dimmons team.

Figure 1: Dimmons research approaches

Areas of interest in research

Traditionally to the methodological and topic shared interests and expertise described above, the content analysis (Figure 2) of the different presentations of the group members and collaborators allowed to identify commonalities as well as to discover shared areas of interest. From social and people-centric views of the scientific activity and impact, to issues of transformation or economic processes, and its relation to economy, media, policies and in a broader sense the political domain.

Figure 2: Tagcloud generated after content analysis of the introductions of group members

Methodological orientation

Another key aspect for developing the strategic planning has been to initially identify the different interests to research methods and approaches within the wider scale of collaborators of the Dimmon group. Ranging from more qualitative to more quantitative methods, as well as wider fields of research, results showed a relevant expertise with interviews and observational methods, while less members of the group were used to apply quantitative approaches such as surveys or lab experiments (Figure 3). On the other hand, approaches like action-research, desk research or co-design were very familiar for a relevant percentage of the group composition.

Figure 3: Experience with research methods and approaches

Although not exhaustive, these first visualizations allowed to identify later on in the strategic planning process areas of improvement and implications for the group composition in the mid and long term.

Map of the ecosystem

Another important part of the analysis stage of the planning was to start to identify the external environment in which the group operates, and for this an important activity was to collectively map the different institutions and agents with which Dimmons collaborates or has a relevant relationship, considering in the perspective the concept of the Quadruple Helix (Carayannis & Campbell, 2012). Again, the process elicited from participants about their perception in their specific context related to their research activity (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Visualization of the ecosystem of the group as a quadruple helix model.

Previous to the map version of the ecosystem of organisations around Dimmons, results from the initial survey allowed to discuss what participants considered important actors and agents from their perspective and with whom the team has connections, clustered in the following table:

International research organizations	Berkman center - Harvard University (USA) and NoC network
	MIT (USA)
	CECAN (UK)
	ÖAW - Austrian academy of sciences (AU)
	Universidad cooperativa Unicoop (México)
	UNAM (México)
	EUI and Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa (Italy)
	Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte (Brasil)
	University of Porto - Sociology (Portugal)
Local research organizations	IGOP UAB
	IBEI
	UPC
	UPF
	Institute for Social Innovation - ESADE
	OpenSystems BCN - UB
	Sociology Dept UB
	IAAC - Institute of Advanced Architecture Catalonia
	Blanquerna - URLL
	UVic
UOC departments / groups	Tecnopolítica (IN3)
	Open Evidence (Spinoff)
	Information and Communication Sciences Studies
	Cooperation area (UOC)
	Humanity Studies (Open Science group)
	Economy Studies (UOC)
	Vicerectorat Globalizació (UOC)
Law Studies (UOC)	

EU funded projects	Euryka Project
	EU projects in Emilia
	EU MP on platform economy
	EUGive project
	EUCity
	ERCs on Blockchain (Samer Hassan and Bodo)
	DECODE
	STEM4Youth
International networks	SmartIB
	Transition Design
	DESI Network
	Systemic Design.net
	Society for Social Studies of Science (4S)
	Community media forum Europe
	Collaborating housing Europe
	OuiShare
Local focused networks	Mares project (Madrid)
	Grupo "Dinero & Valores"
	Oxfam Intermon
	Xarxa d'Economia Solidària de Cat (XES)
	Fem Procomuns / FKI
	Holon
	Ideograma
	REAS Madrid
	BarCola
	CoBOI
	Tecnocampus Mataró

	Fundació Cidob (grupo de dinámicas interculturales)
	Hidra cooperative
Other orgs international	Coop Des Comuns (FR)
	Data Commons experts (FR)
	EnCommuns project (FR)
	Futureplaces.org (PT)
	P2P Foundation (EU)
Media / Communication	Sentit Crític
	Alternativas economicas
	Critical newspaper Mapa
	Eldiario.es
	Global Voices
Public administrations	DG Connect EC
	Barcelona City Council
	Generalitat de Catalunya

3.2 Competitive and SWOT analyses

Competitive analysis (benchmarking)

An additional activity at this stage, conducted in this case via the core participants of the group, was to identify similar groups and initiatives, benchmarking potential competitors and references for the group in relation to their activity and philosophy.

Local inspirational benchmarking:

- **Open Systems Barcelona:** <http://www.ub.edu/opensystems/> - Multidisciplinary group of the University of Barcelona that focuses on arts and public participation as core elements of the way of doing science. They work together with many actors and build tailored-made research collectives to address concerns and issues mostly grounded in urban contexts.
- **ESADE Institute for Social Innovation:** <http://www.esade.edu/research-webs/eng/socialinnovation> - The institute's mission is to develop personal and organisational skills within the business community and nonprofit organisations in order to strengthen their activities and their contribution to a more just and sustainable world. .
- **Fem Procomuns / Free Knowledge Institute:** <http://freeknowledge.eu/> - FKI is a non-profit organisation that fosters equal access to tools for production and exchange of knowledge in all areas of society. Inspired by the Free Software movement, the FKI promotes freedom of use, modification, copying and distribution of knowledge in several different but closely related fields.
- **Ideas for change:** <https://www.ideasforchange.com/> - Open, collaborative strategies for exponential growth of businesses or organizations. Generators of innovation for impact.
- **Opcions:** <http://opcions.org/> - Only means of communication specialized in conscious consumption. Created more than fifteen years ago, it offers information and criteria to consume less and better.
- **Universitat de València (The regulation of sharing economy Group):** <https://www.uv.es/uvweb/research-service/en/research-groups/grup-1285949714098.html?p2=GIUV2015-233> - The group is made up of professors and researchers who have been developing various projects together aimed at

studying the regulation of various sectors of economic activity, understood in a broad sense.

International inspirational benchmarking:

- **Berkman center (USA):** <https://cyber.harvard.edu/> - The Berkman Klein Center for Internet & Society is a research center at Harvard University that focuses on the study of cyberspace. Founded at Harvard Law School, the center traditionally focused on internet-related legal issues.
- **NESTA (UK):** <https://www.nesta.org.uk/> - Innovation foundation that acts through a combination of programmes, investment, policy and research, and the formation of partnerships to promote innovation across sectors.
- **Public Lab (USA):** <https://publiclab.org/> - A community where scientifics, amateur researchers and other participants from civil society can learn how to investigate environmental concerns. Using inexpensive DIY techniques, seeks to change how people see the world in environmental, social and political terms.
- **Sydney University Policy Lab (Australia):** <https://sydney.edu.au/research/centres/sydney-policy-lab.html> - Provides an independent, neutral space to try, test and iterate different approaches and ways of thinking in relation to public policies. Their aim is to catalyse new approaches by finding insights at the intersection of disciplines and expertise.
- **University of Minnesota's Initiative on the Sharing Economy (USA):** <http://sharingeconomy.umn.edu/> - This research initiative tries to shed light on the growing trend away from the exclusive ownership and consumption of resources to one of shared use and consumption. Peer-to-peer shared mobility is a particular focus
- **Center for open innovation in Science (Austria):** <https://ois.lbg.ac.at/> - Established as a leading international hub for investigating and experimenting with Open Innovation research practices. The LBG OIS Center generates and disseminates insights into the use of Open Innovation principles and methods in science, along the entire process to originate new scientific research.

Strategic diagnosis (SWOT analysis)

The analysis of the internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats of the Dimmons group, was conducted in between the analysis and development stages of the strategic planning. First, eliciting about the different SWOT elements via an online survey, and during a second workshop clustering and discussing the results among all participants. This allowed to have a divergence moment where a considerable number of factors were generated, and then a second one of intense convergence and synthesis where the main ones were identified and given a specific category.

Dimmons SWOT	FAVOURABLE	UNFAVOURABLE
I N T E R N A L	Strengths: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Multidisciplinary focus 2. Cutting-edge approach 3. Transversal impact 4. High motivation 5. Open experimentation 6. Wide reputation 	Weaknesses: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Early stage of the group 2. Complexity of action approach 3. Team dispersion 4. Ineffective departmental relationships
E X T E R N A L	Opportunities: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Commons "momentum" 2. Interest from stakeholders 3. Transformation of research for impact 4. Barcelona context 5. New streams for funding 	Threats: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rigid university frameworks 2. Unstable topic background 3. Complexities of applying for funding 4. Changing political agendas 5. High demand pressure

Table summarising the main SWOT elements identified in relation to Dimmons.

The analysis required also internal meetings of the "core" participants of the group to process the information generated so far, then sharing summary documents to make sure the rest of participants validated the results and had a second chance to inform the process and provide feedback about it.

Strengths identified

Multidisciplinary focus	Heterogeneity of hard and soft skills
	Diversity
	Multidisciplinarity
	Multidisciplinarity, multi methodological approaches
	Multidisciplinarity
	Multidisciplinary team
	member's diversity and transdisciplinarity
	Its interdisciplinarity and, connected to that, the different fields of expertise we have.
	Diversity of analysis methodologies
	A great spectrum of practical methodologies so as to be adopted in action-research processes.
Cutting-edge approach	An holistic vision of the subjects related to the group focus.
	The potential to meta-experiment with Commons values
	connecting global and local debates
	An innovative and timely research agenda
	The fact that is getting more international over time, because it opens up more possibilities
	the intersection of topics, digital, commons, gender perspectives, designerly methods, etc
High motivation	enthusiasm
	Motivation; we believe what we do
	Believe and put passion on what we are doing
	commitment
Transversal impact	Its full approach to action-research
	A great connection between action and research in terms of improving digital commons projects and the public policies that should facilitate its expansion and impact.
	Co-creation, social impact
	The will of Dimmons to transcend and impact beyond the academic sphere and its traditional walls.
	working together with civil society/social movements and stakeholders
	Action-research: direct connections to people and organizations working in the field

	(and not just distant, academic observers).
Open experimentation	Openness, in its many aspects.
	the work culture, agile, startup ish
	The flexibility for adapting to changes
	Clear communication
	Agility
Wide reputation	ambition to play at the league of first quality research centres
	CV Excellence and social reputation
	International network: participation in transnational projects; team members from a diversity of countries.
	Barcelona: the research group is based in one of the most prolific places in the world concerning the commons.

Weaknesses identified

Team dispersion	Striving for counter-cultural social change
	use of different languages
	Unknowing what the peers and doing and can do
	geographical distance of (some) participants
	Perhaps the lack of cohesion due to not being together?
	difficulty in finding informal spaces for exchange of opinions and feedbacks with group members when it comes to focusing and redirecting individual investigations
Early stage	A small team related to the group ambition and external petitions
	Lack of balance between too many people in a formation stage and few with senior research / postdoc skills
	Dimension: very few researchers from the team can commit full-time to the related projects
	It's still a very young project
	Lack of a visible strategic plan
Ineffective departmental relationships	Traditional academy values and proceedings
	A lack of an strategy to lead well with OSRT bureaucratic complexity. Frustration generated with this
	University framework limitations

Complexity of action approach	Deep alienation between everyday work and the big objectives
	Too much dispersion and dedication to collaborations that does not feed Dimmons sustainability
	Knowledge co-creation, transversality... takes more time and effort
	As a result of our interdisciplinarity, one of the weaknesses we have is that sometimes we lack cohesion in our definitions and conceptual frameworks
	It has many opportunities knocking at its door regularly
	Difficulty to find people that combine good CV and good researcher skills and Dimmons action approach

Opportunities identified

Interest from stakeholders	The same with methodologies used in local (projects/public policies) adoption.
	have a dialogue with institutions and stakeholders, making research more relevant
	the wave of digitalisation of the social and solidarity economy
	Doing more research-action and more policy-oriented research with actors in the field such as cityhalls, government institutions or platform coops, especially outside of Barcelona. Following our global approach, there's a lot we do that could be fruitful in other cities.
	contact with social actors
Barcelona context	the local environment in barcelona
	sexy barcelona
	Barcelona city
	The links with the Barcelona City Council
	The possibility to show the Barcelona ecosystem outside, as a model of we are one of the main actors.
Commons "Momentum"	Bring commons to new frontiers and achieve goals that other actors of the ecosystem can not achieve or perform (such as FKI, Ouisahare, Ideas for Change) by providing a research pillar and university institution repertoire of actions and resources to the commons ecosystem
	It's a time where alternative approaches to economy and technology (and other domains) point clearly to the Commons
	Action-research with commons oriented orgs.
	Bring commons to new frontiers and achieve goals that other actors of the ecosystem can not achieve or perform (such as FKI, Ouisahare, Ideas for Change) by providing a research pillar and university institution repertoire of actions and resources to the

	commons ecosystem
Transformation of research for impact	The socioeconomic situation that exists
	Match between social needs and the subjects of research
	confront with people having very different expertise
	make investigation with relevant social goals, connecting research and activism
	The Academy is now open to risky solutions in the middle of a wide crisis
	Be a reference for change! demonstrate with facts that there are estatements and university research groups that want to break with the classic corsets
New streams for funding	A small number of research groups with this holistic perspective
	Its reputation in short time
	Well positioned internationally
	The subjects of research are being funded by EU. They are relevant issues
	possibility of fitting into different transversal European projects of social innovation

Threats identified

Rigid university frameworks	Profit networks as facebook are colonizing academia and promoting their own concept of open science
	The possibility of not reaching enough Academic impact in short time
	Bureaucracy inherent to the university/sector
	Sexist dynamics and gender discrimination to Dimmons IP (it can damage Dimmons impact requiring more effort for gaining recognition and also disrupt internal Dimmons dynamics)
	University framework limitations
High demand pressure	The increasing of petitions number and the possibility to give answer to them.
	To maintain the wide spectrum of objectives perspective if we no amplify the core team in a short team.
Unstable topic background	Being co-opted by the "establishment": as the commons become more "trendy", new initiatives pop-up using that label but following questionable processes (vide Ouishare).
	core values of the research being part of buzzes or trends or waves, will the group be relevant in 5 years?
	The confusion "corporate-pro-commons" type in the field of action
	Perception and positioning Dimmons as an "activist", only social (not economical) and radical ghetto group, not being able to gain an hegemonic referent position.

	to create research impactful for a broad part of society, beyond margins
Complexities of applying for funding	Public institutions foster profit industries
	lack of fundings
	The lack of potential resources for funding in the short/mid future
	To the time required in getting a great founding sources.
	The competition with of other research groups interested in being part of competitive processes (Eu projects, IN3 recognition etc)
Changing political agendas	Change of the current political context: the group is very close to the local political authorities, which might change in the future.
	political assimilation with local parties at a city or catalan govt
	Invisibility of Dimmons effort and value by administration centralism in our work with Barcelona City Council.
	the risk of being perceived as a partidistic group (linked only to the Govern at Barcelona).

3.3 Strategic plan

Six strategic objectives for 2018-2023

After the identification of potential strategic objectives connected to the SWOT analysis and rest of knowledge co-generated around the research group, through a series of iterations and a survey there was a definition and prioritization of the following strategic objectives:

O1: REFERENCE PUBLICATIONS - Generate a high-quality research corpus of theoretical framework on socio-economic innovation

Actions derived from this strategic objective have to do with publishing on top academic journals (specially open access) but also participation in conferences or supporting alternative publications with rigorous content. To become a reference in the field though original and high level generated expertise.

O2: OPEN TOOLS - Contribute to processes in action for the resolution of social challenges by developing research-based resources

Generate practical open content (data, etc) and open source tools (toolkits, tutorials, indicators, apps, etc) that can have impact beyond academic community, and favor exploitation of results with actions in the field.

O3: ECOSYSTEM BUILDING - Consolidate a glocal network of partner organizations for quadruple helix collaboration to favour social impact and resilience

To reinforce wide alliances with cities and public policy innovation, as well as other economic actors, with activities and events to generate change as well as practical knowledge.

O4: EMPOWERED TEAM - Consolidate the team with complementary backgrounds, healthy environment and gender-balanced talent

Actions for new and talented scholarships or academic stays the group, and also to agreements with new members expert in complementary fields, as well as actions for a healthy work environment and mutual care, or an internal gender balance.

O5: CATALYTIC SUSTAINABILITY - Obtain funding for action-research from competitive calls with high impact and visibility

Create a diverse and resilient funding scheme. Applying to EU calls or other public funding, to local programs or alliances where we get resources by providing research services.

O6: UNIVERSITY SHIFT - Engage with open access, Commonification processes, transdisciplinarity, Agile and other changing paradigms in the academic culture

Actions oriented to "hack" the academic process from within (specially improving institutional processes and performance), but also experimenting with civic participation in science and responsible research and innovation (RRI).

TOWS matrix

The TOWS Analysis is a variant of the SWOT Analysis, used to generate, compare and select strategies.

After using a SWOT at the beginning of the planning process, the TOWS approach afterwards allowed to decide upon ways forward, basically with a first identification via a specific meeting of the potential strategies to adopt considering the combination of threats, opportunities, weaknesses and strengths.

<p>From SWOT to TOWS <i>Objectives connected to Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (ordered from more to less recurrent) derived from Dimmons SWOT analysis</i></p>	<p>External Opportunities (O):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Commons "momentum" 2. Interest from stakeholders 3. Transformation of research for impact 4. Barcelona context 5. New streams for funding 	<p>External Threats (T):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rigid university frameworks 2. Unstable topic background 3. Complexities of applying for funding 4. Changing political agendas 5. High demand pressure
<p>Internal Strengths (S):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Multidisciplinary focus 2. Cutting-edge approach 3. Transversal impact 4. High motivation 5. Open experimentation 6. Wide reputation 	<p>"Maxi-Maxi" - Strategies that use strengths to maximize opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OPEN TOOLS: Contribute to processes in action for the resolution of social challenges by developing research-based resources (S2+S3/O1+O3): Matches IN3 objectives OE4, OE8 + SDG goals 8, 9 + RRI Public engagement & Open access indicators • UNIVERSITY SHIFT: Engage with open access, Commonification processes, transdisciplinarity, Agile and other changing paradigms in the academic culture (S4+S5/O2+O5): Matches IN3 objectives OE4, OE7 + SDG goals 4, 11 + RRI Public engagement, Science education & Open access indicators 	<p>"Maxi-Mini" - Strategies that use strengths to minimize threats:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REFERENCE PUBLICATIONS: Generate a high-quality research corpus of theoretical framework on socio-economic innovation (S1+S2/T1+T2): Matches IN3 objectives OE1, OE2, OE4 + SDG goals 8, 10, 11, 12 + RRI Ethics indicator

<p>Internal Weaknesses (W):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Early stage of the group 2. Complexity of action approach 3. Team dispersion 4. Ineffective departmental relationships 	<p>"Mini-Maxi" - Strategies that minimize weaknesses by taking advantage of opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ECOSYSTEM BUILDING: Consolidate a glocal network of partner organizations for quadruple helix collaboration to favour social impact and resilience (W1+W2/O2+O4): Matches IN3 objectives OE7, OE10 + SDG goals 16,17 + RRI Governance indicator ● CATALYTIC SUSTAINABILITY: Obtain funding for action-research from competitive calls with high impact and visibility (O3+O5/W1+W2): Matches IN3 objectives OE5, OE2 + SDG goals 12, 3 + RRI Open access indicator 	<p>"Mini-Mini" - Strategies that minimize weaknesses and avoid threats:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EMPOWERED TEAM: Consolidate the team with complementary backgrounds, healthy environment and gender-balanced talent (W1+W4/T3+T5): Matches IN3 objectives OE3, OE6, OE9 + SDG goals 5, 9 + RRI Gender equality & Governance indicators
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Actions and key performance indicators (KPI)

Finally, for this first version of the strategic plan of the research group and planning stage, the different actions derived from each objective and its corresponding key performance indicators are summarised in this section.

For reaching them, there was a first session with the direction of Dimmons and afterwards an open document to reflect ideal scenarios and potential actions derived from them, all related to the previous analyses. This was followed by a second survey to validate and highlight those objectives and actions that had more support from the team and collaborators around the group.

Dimmons strategic objective	Actions	Indicators
O1: REFERENCE PUBLICATIONS 	O1.1 Increase in scientific production	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Indexed articles for IP (ISI), postdocs and PhD candidates (per year) 2. Publications in Quartiles 1-4 (for same categories) 3. Book chapters and books (publishers with impact)
	O1.2 Useful resources to streamline paper publications	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Internal resource for sprint writing, reviewing and submitting papers 2. Shared database for journals and conferences 3. Index of papers under preparation
	O1.3 Series of internal/external seminars	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Doctor Dimmons seminars 2. Annual conference (Procomuns)
	O1.4 Active participation in international academic networks	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conferences participating as paper givers or keynotes 2. Posters in conferences 3. Membership as peer-reviewers in publications

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Memberships of academic boards of projects / journals 5. Not attendance to conference as mere participants
	O1.5 Responsive research agenda for aligning theory with new tendencies	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Search report on queries to Google and other tools about tendencies 2. Collaborations with experts and practitioners in other fields
<p>O2: OPEN TOOLS</p>	O2.1 Communication plan and new Dimmons website platform as repository in accordance with the strategic plan	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dimmons communication strategy plan 2. Improved features of Dimmons website 3. Visit metrics of the website
	O2.2 Replicable and tested toolkit for digital platforms and policy co-creation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Beta version of the toolkit Col-lacy for digital platforms 2. Beta version of the toolkit for policy co-creation 3. Translated versions to English, Spanish, Catalan 4. Downloads from the Dimmons repository and mentions in Social Media 5. Documented use by other researchers, entrepreneurs and policy-related practitioners
	O2.3 Data commons platform for open research and visualizations on collaborative economy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. MVP of the data commons platform in use 2. Beta version of the data commons platform 3. Visit metrics of the platform 4. Data packages contributed by other organisations 5. Publications about the visualizations generated (from Dimmons or other groups)
	O2.4	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Manifesto for action-research impact metrics

	Alternative indicators to research metrics, for social impact of the group	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Shared guidelines for alternative indicators 3. Report about social impact of Dimmons based on the shared guidelines
<p>O3: ECOSYSTEM BUILDING</p>	O3.1 Projection and creation of policy-related links with cities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organisation of Sharing cities meeting 2. Number of agreements or formal alliances with cities
	O3.2 Training track for co-creation & action-research facilitation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Learning materials generated (for UOC or other projects) 2. Courses online about the topic 3. Offline workshops about the project
	O3.3 Dimmons dissemination and media outreach plan	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Communication plan focused on media outreach and advocacy
	O3.4 Master at UOC about collaborative economy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Materials generated for the Master 2. Number of students 3. Experts and organizations collaborating
	O3.5 Shared network agenda for contacts and alliances	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. MVP application of the agenda tool
	O3.6 Closer relation at local level with Generalitat	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Meetings with representatives 2. Projects derived from connecting
	O3.7 Wider intellectual dialogue at local level with other disciplines	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Events attended from other organisations or agents 2. Events organised with other organisations or agents

O4: CATALYTIC SUSTAINABILITY 	O4.1 Strategic competitive proposals and research agreements and contracts	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. IP-oriented funding programs (ERC, ICREA) 2. European funded proposals
	O4.2 Participation in review committees of EU projects	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. EU funded projects with Dimmons as advisors 2. Meetings in Brussels / online for new calls
	O4.3 Strong relation with organization as partners in East Europe	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of an East Europe partner 2. Organizations collaborating 3. Projects in common since collaboration
	O4.4 Cooperativist-oriented spinoff of Dimmons activity	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Viability plan of the spin-off 2. MVP of the service for initial activity 3. Funding derived from activity
	O4.5 Protocol for sharing funds and resources with other organisations	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Defined position of Dimmons in the ecosystem and protocol of monetary relations (when accept retribution from collaborations) 2. Directory of pilots and other collaborations funded via Dimmons
O5: EMPOWERED TEAM 	O5.1 Presenting proposals for attracting talent in competitive competitions of prestige and curricular valorisation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. IP accreditation processes 2. New PhD candidates joining Dimmons with own funding 3. Postdoc winning by Dimmons PhDs 4. Presentation of proposal to join Dimmons by international researchers
	O5.2 Pool of profiles and other resources for detecting and attracting talent	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared directory with collaborators and potential candidates 2. New members of the group, part-time or full-time

	O5.3 Added talent in specific positions for the group	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. New data analysis / development expert 2. New economics / statistical expert 3. Projects related to data analysis and development
	O5.4 Improved capacity for organisation of events and sessions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared “howto” document for practical guidelines 2. Survey for participants in Dimmons events
	O5.5 Team consolidation and Dimmons community	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Workplan “core” team 2. Dimmons community meetings (Grup Recerca Emergent)
	O5.6 Established Dimmons Gender action plan	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Defined Dimmons Equality Plan 2. Internal application and testing of a pilot gender plan
	O5.7 Agenda of celebrations related to achievements and open activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared tool for transversal information about dates and goals 2. Internal events and celebrations
	O5.8 Program of skill and expert development for group members	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Individual courses for expanding skills and background of the team 2. Collective learning experiences as team
	O5.9 Shared resource for welcoming and common knowledge	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Welcome kit to Dimmons with practical info
	O5.10 Protocols for research reflection and respectful convivence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared resource and agreement for personal paces 2. Internal survey for work satisfaction

	O5.11 Code for ethics behaviour and technological sovereignty	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared guidelines for ethical professional and action-research integrity 2. Shared guidelines for technological sovereignty within the group 3. Migrations to open source and ethical tools for regular activity
<p>O6: UNIVERSITY SHIFT</p>	O6.1 Strategic planning, with a co-created methodology	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Published strategic plan 2018-2023 incorporating feedback 2. Academic paper about the process
	O6.2 System of indicators about research and management of the group to track and achieve the strategic planning	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Metrics of performance in Kanboard
	O6.3 Reduction of time dedicated to management and frustration with research services	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Internal "HowTo" document with useful protocols 2. Research assistant position (part-time) 3. Proposals of improvement and critics of functionalities
	O6.4 Interdisciplinary activities with technology-oriented research groups	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared action or initiative with a IT-related group, from UOC or external
	O6.5 Methodological experimentation & design of new co-creation methods	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Documented sessions for co-designing methods and materials 2. Tested methods and materials 3. Paper about the meta-process

	<p>O6.6 New appropriated formats as channels of publication and research dissemination</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Events related to new formats and channels for research culture 2. MVP publication of P2P citizen science journal 3. MVP of art and performance communication of science
	<p>O6.7 Amplified expertise in post-normal and future studies</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Events related to the field 2. Publications connecting with the theoretical framework
	<p>O6.8 Joined forces with civic processes to foster knowledge shifts between academia-society</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Documented meetings and events with civil society actors 2. Publication about the process 3. Campaign in favor of open knowledge

Calendarization

The following gantt chart illustrates the tentative Dimmons strategic plan calendarization until 2023, trimester by trimester, with the dependency relationships between activities and schedule status.

Objectives	Actions	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
O4: (Red)	O4.3			■	■	■
	O4.4		■	■		
	O4.5			■	■	■
O5: Empowered team (Orange)	O5.1	■	■	■	■	■
	O5.2	■	■	■	■	■
	O5.3		■	■	■	
	O5.4		■	■	■	■
	O5.5	■	■	■	■	■
	O5.6	■	■	■	■	■
	O5.7		■	■	■	■
	O5.8		■	■	■	■
	O5.9	■	■	■	■	■
	O5.10		■	■	■	■
	O5.11		■	■	■	
O6: University shift (Purple)	O6.1	■	■	■	■	■
	O6.2		■	■	■	■
	O6.3	■	■	■	■	■
	O6.4		■	■	■	■
	O6.5		■	■	■	■
	O6.6		■	■	■	■
	O6.7		■	■	■	■
	O6.8		■	■	■	■

4. Next steps

For this version of the strategic planning, the actions and KPI for 2018 have been already defined, after an internal consultation and connection with the IN3 strategic goals for the current year. However, for a second version of this document there's currently an ongoing survey among participants in the process, in order to visualize prioritizations and preferences for the next 4 years until 2023.

Additionally, a final round of interviews with a limited number of experts in science, public policies, technology and action-research for feedback and contrast is planned, in order to discuss details of the planning and its general approach. Among them, leaders of institutions related to Dimmons ecosystem like the IN3 direction, I2Cat center or IGOP research group.

☰ 1c Would you add more actions related to this strategic objective?

3 out of 9 people answered this question

Promote peer work within the group to achieve this goal (eg: writing/reading groups)

8 days ago

Take care about to being presence (writing, interviews...) in divulgative publications.

11 days ago

Screenshots of some of the questions of the internal strategic survey.

As a final step, in the following and final phase there's the need as well to visualize and agree on a detailed schedule and roadmap with the research plan, according to a co-defined prioritisation and sequence of each action. This will lead to an integration of the plan with a management system of the day-to-day activities according to Agile principles.

5. References

- Ahlstrand, B., Lampel, J., & Mintzberg, H. (2001). *Strategy Safari: A Guided Tour Through The Wilds of Strategic Management*. Simon and Schuster.
- Amrollahi, A., & Rowlands, B. (2017). Collaborative open strategic planning: a method and case study. *Information Technology & People, 30*(4), 832-852.
- Andersen, T. J. (2004). Integrating decentralized strategy making and strategic planning processes in dynamic environments. *Journal of management studies, 41*(8), 1271-1299.
- Arnold, E., Rush, H., Bessant, J., & Hobday, M. (1998). Strategic planning in research and technology institutes. *R&D Management, 28*(2), 89-100.
- Barzelay, M., & Jacobsen, A. S. (2009). Theorizing implementation of public management policy reforms: A case study of strategic planning and programming in the European Commission. *Governance, 22*(2), 319-334.
- Bemelmans, T. (1979). Strategic planning for research and development. *Long Range Planning, 12*(2), 33-44.
- Berkley, S., Bertram, K., Delfraissy, J. F., Draghia-Akli, R., Fauci, A., Hallenbeck, C., ... & Piot, P. (2010). The 2010 scientific strategic plan of the Global HIV Vaccine Enterprise. *Nature medicine, 16*(9), 981.
- Best, K. M., Jarrín, O., Bутtenheim, A. M., Bowles, K. H., & Curley, M. A. (2015). Innovation in creating a strategic plan for research within an academic community. *Nursing outlook, 63*(4), 456-461.
- Binswanger, M. (2014). Excellence by Nonsense: The Competition for Publications in Modern Science. In *Opening Science* (pp. 49-72). Springer, Cham.
- Boardman, C., & Gray, D. (2010). The new science and engineering management: cooperative research centers as government policies, industry strategies, and organizations. *The Journal of Technology Transfer, 35*(5), 445-459.
- Bonney, R., Shirk, J. L., Phillips, T. B., Wiggins, A., Ballard, H. L., Miller-Rushing, A. J., & Parrish, J. K. (2014). Next steps for citizen science. *Science, 343*(6178), 1436-1437.
- Burke, W. W., Richley, E. A., & DeAngelis, L. (1985). Changing leadership and planning processes at the lewis research center, national aeronautics and space administration. *Human Resource Management, 24*(1), 81-90.

-
- Carayannis, E. G., & Campbell, D. F. (2012). Mode 3 knowledge production in quadruple helix innovation systems. In *Mode 3 Knowledge Production in Quadruple Helix Innovation Systems* (pp. 1-63). Springer, New York, NY.
- Derrick, G., & Alicen Nickson, M. A. (2014). Invisible intermediaries: A systematic review into the role of research management in university and institutional research processes. *Journal of Research Administration*, 45(2), 11.
- Dooris, M. J., Kelley, J. M., & Trainer, J. F. (2004). Strategic planning in higher education. *New Directions for Institutional Research*, 2004(123), 5-11.
- Drummond, C. N. (2003). Strategic planning for research administration. *Journal of Research Administration*, 34(2), 4.
- Eppler, M. J., & Platts, K. W. (2009). Visual strategizing: the systematic use of visualization in the strategic-planning process. *Long Range Planning*, 42(1), 42-74.
- Fuster-Morell, M. (2010). *Governance of online creation communities: Provision of infrastructure for the building of digital commons* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Gibbons, M., Limoges, C., Nowotny, H., Schwartzman, S., Scott, P., & Trow, M. (1994). *The new production of knowledge: The dynamics of science and research in contemporary societies*. Sage.
- Gray, D. O. (2008). Making team science better: Applying improvement-oriented evaluation principles to evaluation of cooperative research centers. *New Directions for Evaluation*, 2008(118), 73-87.
- Holliman, Richard; Adams, Anne; Blackman, Tim; Collins, Trevor; Davies, Gareth; Dibb, Sally; Grand, Ann; Holti, Richard; McKerlie, Fiona; Mahony, Nick and Wissenburg, Astrid eds. (2015). *An Open Research University*. Milton Keynes: The Open University.
- Jasanoff, S. (2003). Technologies of humility: citizen participation in governing science. *Minerva*, 41(3), 223-244.
- Leischow, S. J., Best, A., Trochim, W. M., Clark, P. I., Gallagher, R. S., Marcus, S. E., & Matthews, E. (2008). Systems thinking to improve the public's health. *American journal of preventive medicine*, 35(2), S196-S203.
- Ordorika, I., & Lloyd, M. (2015). International rankings and the contest for university hegemony. *Journal of Education Policy*, 30(3), 385-405.
- Owen, R., Macnaghten, P., & Stilgoe, J. (2012). Responsible research and innovation: From science in society to science for society, with society. *Science and public policy*, 39(6), 751-760.
- Pohl, C., Krütli, P., & Stauffacher, M. (2017). Ten reflective steps for rendering research societally relevant. *GAI- Ecological Perspectives for Science and Society*, 26(1), 43-51.
- Poister, T. H. (2010). The future of strategic planning in the public sector: Linking strategic management and performance. *Public Administration Review*, 70(s1).

-
- Reason, P., & Bradbury, H. (Eds.). (2008). *Handbook of action research: Participative inquiry and practice*. Sage.
- Ribeiro, B. E., Smith, R. D., & Millar, K. (2016). A Mobilising Concept? Unpacking Academic Representations of Responsible Research and Innovation. *Science and engineering ethics*, 1-23.
- Sá, C. M., & Tamtik, M. (2012). Strategic planning for academic research. *Higher Education Management and Policy*, 24(1), 1-20.
- Schelig, K., & Friesike, S. (2014). Putting open science into practice: A social dilemma?. *First Monday*, 19(9).
- Schildhauer, T., & Voss, H. (2014). Open innovation and crowdsourcing in the sciences. In *Opening Science* (pp. 255-269). Springer, Cham.
- SDSN Australia/Pacific (2017): Getting started with the SDGs in universities: A guide for universities, higher education institutions, and the academic sector. Australia, New Zealand and Pacific Edition. Sustainable Development Solutions Network – Australia/Pacific, Melbourne.
- Sanders, E., and Stappers, P. J. (2008). 'Co-creation and the new landscapes of design'. *Co-design* 4(1), pp. 5-18.
- Senabre, E., Ferran-Ferrer, N., & Perelló, J. (2018). Participatory design of citizen science experiments. *Comunicar*, 26(54), 29-38.
- Sidler, M. (2014). Open Science and the Three Cultures: Expanding Open Science to all Domains of Knowledge Creation. In *Opening Science* (pp. 81-85). Springer, Cham.
- Spinuzzi, C. (2005). The methodology of participatory design. *Technical communication*, 52(2), 163-174.
- Srinivasa Rao, A. B., Kumar, P. M., & Aithal, P. S. (2015). Strategic Planning in Higher Education Institutions: A Case Study of SIMS-VISION 2025.
- Vom Brocke, J., & Lippe, S. (2015). Managing collaborative research projects: A synthesis of project management literature and directives for future research. *International Journal of Project Management*, 33(5), 1022-1039.
- Wang, J., & Hicks, D. (2015). Scientific teams: Self-assembly, fluidness, and interdependence. *Journal of Informetrics*, 9(1), 197-207.
- Wilbon, A. D. (2012). Interactive planning for strategy development in academic-based cooperative research enterprises. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 24(1), 89-105.
- Wilson, I. (1994). Strategic planning isn't dead—it changed. *Long range planning*, 27(4), 12-24.